

Determining The Attitudes and Participation Intentions of Tourism Faculty Students Towards Traditional Games and Sports

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Received: 04.02.2026 Accepted: 20.04.2026 Published: 20.05.2026</p> <p>Keywords: Traditional games and sports, Attitude Participation intention, Intangible cultural heritage, Tourism students.</p> <p>Jel Code: L83, Z32</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Bedriye Çilem SOYLU</p> <p>Research Article</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20297670</p>	<p>The aim of this research is to determine the relationship between the attitudes of tourism faculty students towards traditional Turkish sports and games, which are included in the scope of intangible cultural heritage, and their intentions to participate in these activities. The research population consists of students from the Faculty of Tourism at Balikesir University, and the study was conducted using 255 valid questionnaires. Attitude scales towards traditional sports and games and intention-to-participate scales were used as data collection tools. The study focused on traditional Turkish archery and the traditional intelligence and strategy game Mangala, both included in the list of intangible cultural heritage. The obtained data were analyzed using normal distribution tests, exploratory factor analysis, and regression analysis. The findings reveal that although students have a relatively high awareness of traditional sports and games, their participation levels in these activities are quite low. According to the regression analysis results, social and cognitive attitudes towards traditional archery have a significant and positive effect on the intention to participate, while cultural attitudes did not have a significant effect. In the Mangala game, socio-cultural attitudes had a significant effect on the intention to participate, while cognitive attitudes did not..</p>

Introduction

The concept of Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) is defined in the 2003 Convention on the Intangible Cultural Heritage in Paris as "practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills and related instruments, tools and cultural spaces that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals, identify as part of their cultural heritage" (Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2026a). ICH values are evaluated in five main groups: oral traditions and expressions along with language, which serves as a carrier in the transmission of cultural heritage; performing arts; social practices; festivals and rituals; practices related to nature and the universe; and finally, handicrafts. As of January 2026, Turkey has 32 registered intangible cultural heritage values. With this rich list, Turkey is the second country in the world after China, to have registered the most intangible cultural heritage values. When the list is examined, it is seen that traditional sports and games are also under protection. In 2010, Kırkpınar oil wrestling, in 2019 traditional Turkish archery, and in 2020 traditional intelligence and strategy games were added to the list. Traditional Turkish sports can be defined as sporting activities passed down from the past to the present, with functions of competition and entertainment, as well as recreational purposes (Turkey Culture Portal, 2026). At the heart of traditional Turkish sports lie themes of friendship, brotherhood, and bravery. Thanks to their functions of fostering togetherness and social cohesion, traditional sports have maintained their existence throughout history (Karahüseyinoğlu, 2008). However, it can be said that the demand for these sports is decreasing day by day. Therefore, the aim of this research is to determine the attitudes and participation intentions of university students towards traditional Turkish sports and games. The research sample consisted of students from the Faculty of Tourism at Balikesir University. Based on the research findings, suggestions are presented to universities, public institutions and organizations, and researchers to increase students' awareness and interest..

Conceptual Framework / Theory

Culture can be defined as a memory containing the codes of lifestyles that a nation has created throughout its history. Through culture, the interests, perceptions, attitudes, behaviors, and way of life of a society are passed on to future generations as a whole. In short, culture can be described as a distilled summary of a nation's experiences throughout history (Göçer, 2012: 50). Traditional sports and games, which hold an important place in the daily activities of Turks, are an integral part of Turkish folk culture (Karahüseyinoğlu,

2008). Traditional Turkish sports and games are basically divided into two groups: equestrian and non-equestrian sports. Equestrian sports include flat horse racing, beyge, and jump, while non-equestrian sports include games such as bayrak, tomak, çelik-çomak, oil wrestling, and shalvar wrestling. It is known that there are approximately 25 equestrian and 157 non-equestrian sports (İmamoğlu et al., 1997).

The Turkish society has been known as a nomadic people throughout history. Therefore, it has constantly interacted with new cultures in the new geographies it has traveled to. In this way, Turks have carried and taught sports and games, which are a part of their culture, to different geographies (Güven, 1999).

Traditional Oil Wrestling

Oil wrestling is one of the traditional Turkish sports that is believed to have originated in Thrace and the Balkans and has a 4500-year history (World Ethnosport Federation, 2026). The main factor that distinguishes traditional sports from other sports is the customary and ceremonial practices that the sport contains. In this context, oil wrestling, like other traditional sports, consists of cultural concepts. Traditional oil wrestling includes its own unique cultural elements such as oil, the announcer, prayer, greeting, kispet (wrestling attire), peşrev (prelude), music, the institution of the chieftain, and the Kırkpınar tradition (Yıldırım, 2000: 56). What distinguishes oil wrestling from other types of wrestling is that it is a sport that requires balance. In oil wrestling, matches begin with the wrestlers wearing kispet (a leather garment that extends from below the navel to below the knee). Afterwards, the wrestlers are oiled, and the match continues until one wins. During this competition, war tunes are played with drums and zurna (Turkish wind instrument) (Turkish Wrestling Federation, 2026). The traditional Kırkpınar oil wrestling competition was inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2010, representing Türkiye.

Traditional Turkish Archery

Archery is the effort to hit a specific target while shooting an arrow as far as possible through a bow. This sport is the result of combining posture, grip, and shooting techniques with muscle power (İnan, 1992: 2). In addition to physical attributes such as strength, balance, flexibility, speed, body integrity, gross and fine motor skills, it requires intelligence, attention, and concentration during shooting (Türker, 2022). Archery holds a significant place in Turkish folk culture. Historically, Turks have been known by different nations as an archer nation, a people who wielded bows, and those who shot arrows to the sky. Archery and horsemanship, in particular, are concepts synonymous with Turks. Mounted archery and foot archery were the most effective weapon-wielding methods known during the Ottoman period. What makes them so powerful is the technological superiority of the bows (Tuzcuoğulları, 2022). To ensure the continuation of this sport, lodges called kemankeş were established during the Ottoman Empire. The areas where archery was practiced are still known today as archery fields, maintaining their importance (Karcıoğlu and Söylemez, 2022). Traditional Turkish archery was inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2019, representing Türkiye.

Traditional Intelligence and Strategy Game Mangala

Mangala is an intelligence and strategy game that dates back to the earliest periods of humanity. In different cities of Turkey, it is known as: altı ev, hane, mele, han, göçmecik, höme, emme, bızıldı, bızıt, çüş, foduk, pıç, meneli taş, guycuk, kuyucuk taşı, evcik, kuytu, yuf, çal, kuy taşı (Uluişik, 2018). In Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, the game is known as togyzqumalaq, toquz korgool, and göçürme (UNESCO, 2026). The game is suitable for two people or two groups. The aim of the game is for players to collect the most stones (seeds, grains, etc.). The duration of the game can vary depending on the players and the rules (Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2026b). Playing Mangala provides benefits such as cunning, alertness, foresight, flexibility, resilience, prudence, and memory (Kul, 2018: 987). This traditional intelligence and strategy game was registered on the UNESCO Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2020 as a joint file with Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan.

Literature Review

There are limited studies on traditional Turkish sports in the relevant literature. In the study conducted by Şahin and Evli (2020), theses on traditional Turkish sports were examined and only 11 publications were found. When the subject distribution of the theses is evaluated, it is seen that they focus on general sports or branches in a certain period. In line with the aim of the research, studies that deal with traditional Turkish sports within the framework of intangible cultural heritage are listed below. A review of the international literature also reveals a similarly limited number of studies.

The study conducted by Brankov et al. (2026) examined the assessment and preservation status of traditional sports and games within the scope of intangible cultural heritage. The research findings indicate that the promotion of traditional sports and games is largely carried out through event tourism, but community participation in these events is limited. While a significant portion of participants believe that traditional sports and games can be marketed through tourism, inadequacies in knowledge transfer and weak local community support stand out as key obstacles to the sustainability of this heritage. Furthermore, the study found that women and individuals with lower levels of education exhibited more positive attitudes towards traditional sports and games.

Zhang (2025) examined the cultural capital transformation of Wushu, a traditional Chinese martial art, within the scope of intangible cultural heritage, and the impact of this transformation on individuals' social status. The research argues that intangible cultural heritage transforms traditional cultural practices and becomes an important tool in individuals' social positioning.

A review study was conducted by Genç and Kırdemir (2024) examining the sports branches included in the list of intangible cultural heritage. Within the scope of the research, it was determined that sports such as Kırkpınar oil wrestling, traditional archery and mangala are important cultural heritage elements that reflect history and culture and provide value transfer. In addition, it was concluded that various studies are carried out by official institutions in these areas.

The study conducted by Nalcioğlu (2024) aims to determine the awareness of professional sports representatives regarding the cultural heritage related to Kırkpınar oil wrestling, traditional Turkish archery, and mangala, and their participation in the processes of protecting, preserving, and transmitting this heritage. According to the findings, it was observed that the participants had a high level of awareness regarding Kırkpınar oil wrestling, but their level of involvement in the nomination file preparation process was low. Furthermore, it was determined that the participants' awareness of traditional Turkish archery and mangala was at a moderate level, and their level of involvement in the nomination file preparation process was also low.

Karcioğlu and Söylemez (2022) aimed to determine the place and importance of traditional Turkish sports within cultural tourism and to examine the potential contribution of these sports to tourism as a cultural heritage element. As a result of the research, it was determined that traditional Turkish sports are an important historical and cultural heritage, continue to be preserved in different regions, and have high potential in terms of cultural tourism. However, it was determined that these sports are not sufficiently promoted in Turkey and have not yet received the place they deserve in tourism policies.

Luchoro-Parilla et al. (2021) consider traditional sports and games as a component of intangible cultural heritage. In this context, their research examines the cultural heritage nature of traditional games within the framework of an "ethnomotor" approach. The study analyzes 513 traditional games specific to the Canary Islands, evaluating them based on their internal and external characteristics. The research results highlight that traditional games play a significant role in terms of sustainability and environmental harmony due to their use of materials derived from nature. In this respect, traditional games are considered not only recreational activities but also important tools for cultural transmission, social integration, and educational processes.

The aim of the study conducted by Gencay et al. (2018) was to determine the tendencies and awareness of high school students regarding the practice of traditional Turkish sports. The research results show that the sports branches that young people are most interested in and want to practice are sledding and equestrian archery. In contrast, aba wrestling was found to be the least known traditional sport among young people. The research results reveal that young people do not have sufficient knowledge and awareness about some branches of traditional Turkish sports. Overall, the research results show that the level of interest and inclination towards traditional sports is low.

Method

The population of this study consists of students studying at the Faculty of Tourism of Balıkesir University. Due to time and access constraints, the research was limited to a single university, which is considered one of the significant limitations of the study. In sample selection, convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling method, was used. In this context, students who voluntarily participated in the research were included in the sample. A questionnaire was used as the data collection tool in the research. In the creation of the questionnaire, the scale developed by Koçak et al. (2021) to measure attitudes towards traditional sports and games, and the scale used by Akkuş (2013) to measure participation intention, were utilized. However, these scales were not used directly in the current study; instead, they were adapted to traditional archery and mangala games, selected from among the traditional sports and games listed in the ICH list. In the scale adaptation process, the statements were first rearranged to suit the research context, and then the opinions of three academics specializing in tourism and recreation were consulted to ensure content validity. Necessary linguistic and semantic corrections were made in line with expert opinions. In addition, a pilot study was conducted with a limited number of participants to test the comprehensibility of the scale, and the survey form was finalized based on the feedback received. The survey form consists of two sections. The first section includes statements measuring participants' attitudes towards traditional archery and mangala games, and their intention to participate. These statements were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly disagree, 5=Strongly agree). The second section includes questions to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants and their experiences with traditional sports and games. Data were collected between February 1, 2024, and March 30, 2024, using a face-to-face survey method. A total of 300 questionnaires were obtained; after removing incomplete or incorrectly completed questionnaires, 255 valid questionnaires were included in the analyses. Descriptive statistics, normality tests, factor analysis, and regression analysis were applied to the obtained data. The hypotheses developed in line with the relevant literature in this study are as follows:

H1: Attitude towards traditional archery has a significant effect on the intention to participate.

H1a: Social attitudes toward traditional archery have a significant effect on the intention to participate.

H1b: Cognitive attitudes toward traditional archery have a significant effect on the intention to participate.

H1c: Cultural attitudes toward traditional archery have a significant effect on the intention to participate.

H2: Attitudes toward the traditional mangala game have a significant effect on the intention to play the game.

H2a: Socio-cultural attitudes toward the traditional mangala game have a significant effect on the intention to play the game.

H2b: Cognitive attitudes toward the traditional mangala game have a significant effect on the intention to play the game.

Findings

Conclusion and Recommendations

By summarizing the findings, a conclusion section containing theoretical and practical contributions should be created, and suggestions for future studies should be provided.

Various statistical methods were used in the analysis of the data collected in the research. The findings obtained regarding the research are reported in this section.

Table 1. Participant Information

		n	%
Gender	Male	159	62,4
	Female	96	37,6
	Total	255	100
Age	Ages 18-20	152	59,5
	Ages 21-23	93	36,4
	Ages 24 and above	10	4
	Total	255	100
Department	Tourism Guiding	124	48,6
	Tourism Management	46	18,0
	Recreation Management	38	14,9
	Gastronomy and Culinary Arts	47	18,4
	Total	255	100

Continuation of the table			
Year of Study	1	102	40,0
	2	80	31,4
	3	45	17,6
	4	28	11,0
Awareness of Traditional Sports and Games	Aba Wrestling	10	3,9
	Mounted Archery	157	61,6
	Traditional Archery	214	83,9
	Traditional Sledding	43	16,9
	Mangala	137	53,7
	Mounted Cirit	137	53,7
	Cirit	175	68,6
	Şalvar Wrestling	20	7,8
	Traditional Oil Wrestling	201	78,8
Sources of Information	Family	109	42,7
	Friend	115	45,1
	Internet/social media	146	57,3
	TV, newspapers, etc.	146	57,3
	School/faculty	65	25,5
	Other	3	0,8
Previous Participation	Participant	41	16,1
	Non-participant	214	83,9
Sports and games they have previously participated in	Traditional Archery	17	6,7
	Mounted Archery	1	0,4
	Mounted Cirit	1	0,4
	Cirit	3	1,2
	Mangala	22	8,6
	Oil Wrestling	5	2,0
	Traditional Sledding	1	0,4
The sports or games they are currently interested in	Yes	10	3,9
	Equestrian archery, Cirit	1	0,4
	Mangala	3	1,2
	Archery	5	2,0
	No	177	96,7

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the participants and their responses regarding traditional sports or games. 62.4% of the participants were female and 37.6% were male. Regarding age distribution, 59.5% were between 18-20 years old, 36.4% were between 21-23 years old, and 4% were 24 years and older. Looking at the distribution of the departments they were studying, 48.6% were in tourism guiding, 18% in tourism management, 14.9% in recreation management, and 18.2% in gastronomy and culinary arts. 40% of the participants were first-year students, 31.4% were second-year students, 17.6% were third-year students, and 11% were final-year students.

Regarding the sports and games the participants were aware of, archery was the most known sport with 83.9%. Oil wrestling came in second with 78.8%. The least frequent source of information is aba wrestling, at 3.9%. Regarding information sources for traditional sports and games, the internet/social media, TV, newspapers, etc., ranked first with 57.3% of participants. School/faculty came last with 25.5%. It was observed that 16.1% of participants had previously participated in traditional sports or games. Looking at the sports or games they had previously participated in, 8.6% mentioned mangala, 6.7% traditional archery, and 2% oil wrestling. Only 3.9% of participants are currently involved in traditional sports or games.

Factor Analysis

Factor analysis was conducted to examine the construct validity of the variables included in the scale prepared to determine the attitudes and participation intentions of tourism faculty students towards traditional archery and mangala games. For this, it was first checked whether the data were normally distributed. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was performed on the research data, and the data were found to be significant at the $p > .05$ level. Therefore, the kurtosis-skewness values of the data were examined. Since all kurtosis and skewness values were between (+1.5) and (-1.5), it was accepted that the data were normally distributed (Tabachnick and Fidell 2013). The suitability of the data for factor analysis was examined with the sample

adequacy (KMO) coefficient and the Bartlett Sphericity test. In order to perform factor analysis, a KMO sub-value of 0.70 (Altunışık et al. 2012) and a Bartlett's sphericity test value of ≤ 0.05 were used as the basis (Akkoyunlu et al. 2010).

Table 2. Factor Analysis for Attitudes Towards Traditional Archery.

Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Communalities	FACTORS
ArcheryA2	,859			,807	Social Eigenvalue: 3,027 Variance Explained: % 23,286 Mean: 3,73 Cronbach' Alpha: ,842
ArcheryA1	,791			,666	
ArcheryA4	,709			,690	
ArcheryA3	,613			,543	
ArcheryA7		,846		,723	Cultural Eigenvalue: 2,889 Variance Explained: % 22,221 Mean: 4,09 Cronbach' Alpha: ,805
ArcheryA5		,782		,675	
ArcheryA6		,757		,644	
ArcheryA8		,567		,550	
ArcheryA12			,770	,698	Cognitive Eigenvalue: 2,540 Variance Explained: % 19,535 Mean:3,86 Cronbach' Alpha: ,800
ArcheryA10			,745	,698	
ArcheryA13			,683	,655	
ArcheryA11			,556	,535	
ArcheryA9			,468	,571	
Total Variance Explained: % 65,041 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: 870; Barlett Test: χ^2: 1618,340 s.d.:78, p<.001					

A reliability analysis was conducted for the traditional archery attitude scale, and since Cronbach's Alpha (α) value was determined as .894, it was decided to perform factor analysis. KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity Test were performed on the scale, and the KMO value was found to be .870. According to the Bartlett test, the approximation chi-square (χ^2) value was 1618.340, and the significance level was $p=.000$. Based on these results, it is understood that the scale is suitable for factor analysis. The factor analysis of the traditional archery attitude scale revealed three factors. The first factor has an explained variance of 23.286%, an eigenvalue of 3.027, a mean of 3.73, and a reliability of .842. The second factor has an explained variance of 22.221%, an eigenvalue of 2.289, a mean of 4.09, and a reliability of .805. The third factor has an explained variance of 19.535%, an eigenvalue of 2.540, a mean of 3.86, and a reliability coefficient of 800. These factors are named social, cultural, and cognitive, respectively, as in the original scale. The total explained variance of the scale was determined to be 65.041%.

Table 3. Factor Analysis for Intention to Participate in Traditional Archery.

Items	Factor 1	Communalities	FACTORS
ArcheryI2	,955	,911	Intention Eigenvalue: 2,689 Variance Explained: % 89,630 Mean: 2,51 Cronbach' Alpha: ,942
ArcheryI3	,945	,893	
ArcheryI1	,941	,885	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: ,870; Barlett Test: χ^2: 1618,340 s.d.:78, p<.001			

A reliability analysis was conducted for the traditional archery intention-to-participate scale, and since Cronbach's Alpha (α) value was determined to be .942, it was decided to perform factor analysis. The scale's KMO value was found to be .870, and according to the Bartlett test, the approximation chi-square (χ^2) value was 1618.340 with a significance level of $p=.000$. These results indicate that the scale is suitable for exploratory factor analysis (EFA). According to the factor analysis results, the items were grouped under a

single factor, as in the original scale. Accordingly, the explained variance of the scale was determined to be 89.630%, the mean 2.51, and the eigenvalue 2.2689.

Table 4. Factor Analysis of Attitudes Towards Traditional Mangala Game

Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Communalities	FACTORS	
MangalaA6	,879		,782	Social-Cultural Eigenvalue: 4,631 Variance Explained: % 35,619 Mean: 3,69 Cronbach' Alpha: ,912	
MangalaA5	,869		,763		
MangalaA7	,802		,659		
MangalaA4	,719		,668		
MangalaA8	,668		,504		
MangalaA2	,659		,657		
MangalaA1	,636		,650		
MangalaA3	,621		,523		
MangalaA11		,880	,788		Cognitive Eigenvalue: 4,127 Variance Explained: % 31,744 Mean: 4,19 Cronbach' Alpha: ,900
MangalaA10		,869	,794		
MangalaA12		,838	,742		
MangalaA13		,791	,677		
MangalaA9		,651	,549		
Total Variance Explained: % 67,364 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: ,898; Barlett Test: χ^2: 2410,106 s.d.:78, p<.001					

A reliability analysis was conducted for the attitude scale towards the Mangala game. Since Cronbach's Alpha (α) value was determined to be .922, it was decided to perform factor analysis. KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity Tests were performed on the scale, and the KMO value was found to be .898. According to the Bartlett test, the approximation chi-square (χ^2) value was 2410.106, and the significance level was $p=.000$. Based on these results, it is understood that the scale is suitable for factor analysis. The factor analysis revealed two factors. The first factor has an explained variance of 35.619%, an eigenvalue of 4.631, a mean of 3.69, and a reliability of .912. This factor was named social-cognitive. The second factor has an explained variance of 31.744%, an eigenvalue of 4.127, a mean of 4.19, and a reliability of .900. This factor was named cultural. The total explained variance of the scale was determined to be 67.364%.

Table 5. Factor Analysis for Intention to Play Traditional Mangala Game

Items	Factor 1	Communalities	FACTORS
MangalaI3	,946	,894	Intention Eigenvalue: 2,635 Variance Explained: % 87,836 Mean: 1,81 Cronbach' Alpha: ,942
MangalaI2	,935	,874	
MangalaI1	,931	,867	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: ,764; Barlett Test: χ^2: 617,725 s.d.:3 , p<.001			

A reliability analysis was conducted for the intention to participate in the Mangala game scale, and since Cronbach's Alpha (α) value was determined as .931, it was decided to perform factor analysis. The KMO value of the scale is .764, and according to the Bartlett test, the approximation chi-square (χ^2) value is 617.725 and the significance level is $p=.000$. These results show that the scale is suitable for factor analysis. According to the factor analysis results, the items were grouped under a single factor, as in the original scale. Accordingly,

the explained variance of the scale was determined as 87.836%, the mean as 1.81, and the eigenvalue as 2.635. These values are given in Table 8.

Hypothesis Tests (Regression Analysis)

Table 6 presents the results of the regression analysis conducted to measure the effect of social, cultural, and cognitive attitudes towards traditional archery on the intention to participate in traditional archery. The multiple regression model established for the dependent variable (intention to participate) and predictor variables (social, cultural, cognitive) is statistically significant ($F [3;251] = 10.538$ $p < 0.001$). Social, cultural, and cognitive attitude dimensions explain approximately 10% of the variation in intentions to participate in archery. Social and cognitive attitude dimensions have a positive effect on intention to participate in archery (0.392; 0.289), and these relationships are statistically significant ($t_{\text{social}} = 3.014$ $p_{\text{social}} < 0.01$; $t_{\text{cognitive}} = 2.022$ $p_{\text{cognitive}} < 0.05$). The cultural attitude dimension ($t = -1.196$, $p = .232$) did not have a statistically significant effect on intention to participate in archery. In line with these results, H1a and H1b are supported, and H1c is not supported.

Table 6. Effects of Attitude Towards Traditional Archery on Participation Intention.

S, K, B → Intention	β	Std. β	t	p	R	Adjusted R^2	F	p	VIF
Constant	,584	-	1,197	,232					-
Social	,392	,244	3,014	,003	,334	,101	10,538	***	1,849
Cultural	-,158	-,088	1,198	,232					1,510
Cognitive	,289	,169	2,022	,044					1,974

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; regression-residual: 17,862 / 1,695 s.d.:3 - 251

Table 7 presents the results of the regression analysis conducted to measure the effect of socio-cultural and cognitive attitudes towards the mangala game on the intention to participate in the mangala game. The multiple regression model established for the dependent variable (intention to participate) and the predictor variables (socio-cultural, cognitive) is statistically significant ($F [2;251] = 9.555$ $p < 0.001$). The socio-cultural and cognitive attitude dimensions explain approximately 6% of the variation in intentions to participate in the mangala game. The socio-cultural dimension has a positive effect on the intention to participate in the mangala game (0.401), and this relationship is statistically significant ($t_{\text{socio-cultural}} = 3.710$ $p_{\text{socio-cultural}} < 0.001$). The cognitive attitude dimension ($t = -0.187$, $p = 0.852$) did not have a statistically significant effect on the intention to participate in the mangala game. Based on these results, H2a is supported and H2b is not supported.

Table 7. Effects of Attitude Towards Traditional Mangala Game on Intention to Play.

S-K, B → Intention	β	Std. β	t	p	R	Adjusted R^2	F	p	VIF
Constant	1,037	-	2,312	,022					-
Social-Cultural	,401	,273	3,710	,000	,266	,063	9,555	***	1,468
Cognitive	-,023	-,014	-0,187	,852					1,468

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; regression-residual: 16,898 / 1,768 s.d.:2 - 252

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research results show that tourism faculty students are generally familiar with traditional Turkish sports and games, but their level of active participation in these activities remains quite limited. It is noteworthy that, despite relatively high awareness of elements such as traditional archery and mangala, which are included in the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage List, their intention to participate is at a low level. This situation reveals a disconnect between awareness and experience of cultural heritage elements.

When attitudes towards traditional archery were examined, it was found that social and cognitive dimensions significantly influenced the intention to participate, but the cultural dimension did not have a statistically significant effect. This finding shows that although students perceive archery as a cultural value, this perception does not directly translate into a behavioral intention. In the mangala game, socio-cultural

attitude was found to be decisive in the intention to participate, while the cognitive dimension was ineffective. Overall, the results reveal that the intention to participate in traditional sports and games is shaped more by social interaction and experience-oriented elements. In this context, the study contributes to the literature by drawing attention to the role of young people in preserving intangible cultural heritage. Based on the research findings, various suggestions can be developed to ensure the transmission and sustainability of traditional Turkish sports and games to younger generations. Firstly, it is recommended that universities, especially tourism faculties, include more practical courses or workshops on traditional sports and games in their curricula. This would allow students not only to acquire theoretical knowledge but also to experience these cultural heritage elements firsthand.

Public institutions and local governments organizing festivals, promotional days, and practical events in cooperation with universities can encourage students to participate in these activities through social interaction. Furthermore, the effective use of social media and digital platforms can be considered an important tool for attracting the interest of young people. For researchers, conducting similar studies at different universities and with different sample groups will increase the generalizability of the results. In addition, it is recommended that qualitative research methods be used to examine the motivations behind students' intentions to participate in greater depth. Such studies will contribute to the preservation of traditional sports and games and their more effective utilization in the field of tourism.

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Author Contributions

Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft, Supervision, Project Administration.

Author 2: Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing.

Author 3: Investigation, Validation, Resources, Writing – Review & Editing.

(The author contribution statements are defined according to the CRediT taxonomy as follows: Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Validation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Resources; Data curation; Writing – Original draft; Writing – Review & Editing; Visualization; Supervision; Project administration; Funding acquisition.)

Declaration of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

If the authors do have any financial interests or personal relationships that could be considered as potential competing interests, they should be clearly stated here

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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